

THE BLOG AS A STRATEGIC ACTIVE METHODOLOGY APPLIED TO TEXTUAL READING AND PRODUCTION IN SPECIALIZED EDUCATIONAL SERVICE (SES)

 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7295310

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ABSTRACT

This article aims to clearly and objectively demonstrate the importance of taking advantage of technological advances as resources to improve the methodological service to the target audience student, of the Specialized Educational Service (AEE) of state public schools, especially the student with Intellectual Disabilities (ID) light. For this, it was thought to use the Blog to improve reading strategies such as selection, anticipation, inference, verification and production of texts among others. For this, a bibliographic research was carried out to seek the theoretical foundation on the use of the Blog as an active methodology to encourage the practice of reading and the production of texts of different textual, narrative, descriptive, instructive and argumentative genres through intense practice . of silent reading, problem situations, beginning, middle or end elaborations for the story, text puzzles, illustrations, role-plays, practical classes, video recording, presentations in parties, among others. Considering that reading strategies are techniques or methods that readers use to acquire information, or procedures or activities chosen to facilitate the process of reading comprehension. The assessment can be done through observation and practical analysis of reading and writing, by students with mild ID, their attitudes and behaviors towards reading practice, analysis of textual productions according to the genres worked and grammar and records through photographs and videos.

Keywords: Specialized Educational Assistance. Student with mild intellectual disabilities. Blog as active methodology. Reading strategies.

INTRODUCTION

When an individual proposes to carry out a reading, he already has in his mind what type of subject he intends to dedicate himself to, whether it is sport, religion, society, romance,

technology, economy, city, politics, food, among others. This is how the textual genre has also been defined, whether literary or not, narrative, informative, instructive, descriptive, argumentative; the support on which it will reach your hands, whether a magazine, newspaper, book, websites, *blogs*, *WhatsApp*, *Facebook*, *Twitter*, websites, medicine leaflet, assembly instructions, cooking recipes...

When faced with the text, the title, in the form of headlines, already invites the reader into the subject, as well as the pictures, abstracts, the preface and other resources used by the writer. All these instruments become a form of calling for the reader to dive in and continue reading the text until the end.

The reader, when proposing to read, has defined in his thinking the main objective to which he dedicates himself, whether it is to seek information, confirm or refute a hypothesis raised before reading, assemble a device, make a prescription, administer medicine for a sick, to know the opinions of other people, to know what is happening in your city, country or in the world, to establish and maintain dialogues with other people. So how can you also read to illustrate, read to paraphrase, recreate and parody, act out, meditate, study, have fun, etc. Finally, he sets up his reading strategy, performs the reading and achieves his goal.

Silva (1998) answers, in this context, the following question: Why read? For him, reading reaches 3 (three) basic categories, to highlight: information, knowledge and pleasure.

- ✓ *Informational Category* – keeps me up to date on events happening around me, through newspapers and magazines.
- ✓ *Epistemological category* – research and study, permanent study.
- ✓ *category linked to pleasure, aesthetic* – leads to poetry and other literary genres (SILVA, 1998, p. 55).

But to be a reader, it is necessary to learn to read and, above all, to find in reading the inexhaustible source of information, knowledge and pleasure that one seeks. In the sequel, the same author makes the following statement in relation to the formation of student readers:

The formation of a taste for reading depends on the set of interactions, on the educational circuit around books, and all the people involved in the process (including librarians, teachers and parents, etc.) need to know the references intended by the works, feel the beauty of the literary word, they need to live, in practice, the pleasure of reading (Op.Cit.).

So, if the objective of the school is to form citizens capable of seeking in reading the information they need to carry out a certain activity, of being interested in acquiring knowledge about the world that surrounds them and showing themselves capable of using reading as a

source of pleasure and entertainment, it is necessary that she apply strategies that strengthen this practice, especially with students with mild Intellectual Disabilities, considering that reading is a source of linguistic knowledge and information that contribute both to expanding the student's lexicon, as well as their theoretical knowledge on different subjects.

This is because, no person can give his opinion, through written language, or even through speech, if he does not have knowledge about the subject he intends to address; about the people to whom you will write or speak; about the type of text you need to use to send your message or express your opinion.

Izabel Solé (1998), in this regard, argues that “in the context of education, it is necessary for boys and girls to learn to read with different intentions to achieve different goals. In this way, in addition to learning to activate a large number of strategies, they learn that reading can be useful for many things” (p. 42).

In this sense, reading becomes fundamental, both for cognitive and affective development, since, when faced with the subject that interests you, the text will awaken the desire to want to read and reach the end. This wanting is the centerpiece of the entire teaching-learning process. Only those who want to learn learn. In the meantime, teachers need to work on strategies that encourage this desire to learn, especially through the act of reading, commenting on excerpts from read books, reciting small poems, haiku, taking song lyrics to be read and appreciated. Show that he also appreciates the text read, talking about the topic, about the writer, about the illustrations, about intriguing passages and other whys of the story, the subjects and the types of texts used to approach them. All this makes him convince more than just asking the student to read, for example, to then charge in the form of questions in the formal assessment.

As Marisa Lajolo said, quoted by Ezequiel Theodoro da Silva (1994),

[...] Without teachers who read, who like books, who feel pleasure in reading, it is very difficult to change the current landscape of school reading. (...) Even with the fulfillment of all the ideal requirements for effective reading at school, without the presence of teachers properly equipped in written communication, there will not be the slightest possibility of transformation and advancement (LAJOLO, 1982 cited by SILVA, 1994, p. 22).

It is known that before practicing the act of reading, the reader selects the text, whether novel, short story, news, recipe, novel, scientific article, poems, haiku, he manages to anticipate the subject that will be dealt with in the text, through the title, abstracts, book covers, superstructure and textual genre. As he reads, he makes inferences in the text, using his previous

knowledge to do so, checking whether the hypothesis raised in the anticipation was true or not. Finally, he will produce his own intuitive text, in writing or through discussion, taking sides, reflecting or discussing with other people, the subject addressed in the text, because reading will provide him with the expansion of his knowledge in relation to the topic read. , thus expanding their linguistic vocabulary.

However, if the teacher is unaware of this path, these strategies, it will be difficult to create didactic situations that materialize, once, you can only do what you know and master. If the teacher only says or demands reading and writing because he heard that they are important or because the system demands from him results in this sense, he will not be able to convince his student that reading and writing are fundamental social practices for human and for affective and cognitive development.

SELECTION, ANTICIPATION, INFERENCE, VERIFICATION AND TEXT PRODUCTION: STRATEGIES TO IMPROVE TEXT READING AND PRODUCTION PRACTICE

As the teaching-learning process starts very early, the teacher will be able to plan reading teaching strategies for children from an early age, so that they grow up witnessing positive and pleasurable reading practices. Therefore, when encouraging students to read, the teacher needs to consider age, topics of interest, and level of learning, because when offering texts that are too long for students with a level of learning in the early grades, there is a risk of not being able to read and being discouraged in the first pages. Also, you run the risk of offering short and very easy books for students who are already at a more advanced level of learning, and they will find reading boring. Before proposing to offer texts for reading, the teacher needs to consider some criteria.

Reading strategies are techniques or methods that readers use to acquire information, and to facilitate the process of reading comprehension. They are flexible plans adapted to different situations that vary according to the text to be read and the approach previously developed by the reader to facilitate its understanding (DUFFY & Cols., 1987; BROWN, 1994; PELLEGRINI, 1996; KOPKE, 2001, sp.).

In order to better analyze the texts that will be offered to students, however, the teacher needs to have these and other considerations as a starting point, especially the phases of reading. This book considers the definitions of Schli-ebe-Lippret and A. Beinlich cited by R. Bamberger

(2000), regarding the adequacy of the text, considering the interest in each of the child's developmental stages:

a) Age of picture books and nursery rhymes (2 to 5 or 6 years old): Early integral-personal, egocentric phase. The child makes little distinction between the inner and the outer world; it only experiences the environment in which it lives in relation to itself (age of magical thinking). During its development there is a separation between the ego and the environment. Picture books help when they present simple objects, alone, taken from the environment in which the child lives. The next step is to group objects that are usually together and show the child relating to various things in the environment. The child is less interested in the action of the plot than in isolated scenes. He likes nursery rhymes because of the rhythm, the vigorous plasticity of ideas, the rhythm of the game with words and their sounds. His first interest in factual knowledge is satisfied by the simplest of non-fiction picture books. With the first signs of independence and challenge (age 4), independent play with picture books is also important for educational purposes.

b) Age of the fairy tale (from 5 to 8 or 9 years old). Magic realism reading age. At this stage of its development the child is essentially susceptible to fantasy. This is true for all school subjects, even geography and science. At the beginning of this period the child mainly likes fairy tales that represent an environment that is familiar to him. The less she identifies with the characters in fairy tales, the more she appreciates them as games of the imagination, but she will prefer characters and stories from a faraway world of wonders. The pleasure he finds in the rhythm and the verses and the love for poetry remain the same.

c) Age of environmental stories or factual reading (9 to 12 years). Construction of a practical, realistic, rationally ordered facade, against a magical-adventurous-pseudo-realistically masked backdrop.

d) Age of adventure story: adventurous realism or sensationalism-oriented non-psychological reading phase (12 to 14 or 15 years old). During the pre-adolescent development processes, the child, little by little, becomes aware of his own personality; loosens or undoes previous links (second age of independence and challenge). This is the age at which aggression and gang formation predominate. Readers' interest can be aroused primarily through plot, events, and sensationalism. When it comes to a girl, the rebellious child.

e) The years of maturity or the development of the aesthetic-literary sphere of reading (14 to 17 years old). Discovery in one's inner world of critical egocentrism, development of a life plan, development of various scales of values (SHLIEBE-LIPPERT and BEINLICH apud BAMBERGER, 2000, pp. 33-35).

In addition to plot, plot, form and content are also valued as reading material. Interest in the outside world is replaced by participation in the inner world and the world of values. Reading interest: adventure with more intellectual content, travel books, engaging literature, factual material that often relates to vocational preferences.

What is this selection process?

It can be said that it is that moment after the reader decides that he is going to read and, through a cognitive process, selects possible topics that he needs to read from that moment on, driven by the question: *What am I going to read for?* He, then, is motivated by an objective, if he is going to read to acquire information on a certain subject, if it is to acquire knowledge or simply, if he is going to read for pleasure and pleasure. Thus decided, intuitively, he will select the support of the text, whether websites, newspapers, magazines, books, pamphlets, blogs, as well as trace the superstructure of the text, whether scientific book, whether news, short stories, novels, novels, advertisements, recipes, laws, instructions, according to the theme and subjects he wants or needs to read. But, this happens when the student is already a reader and aware of the importance of this act for their self-education and continuous self-education.

Silva (1994), however, makes the following observation regarding the methodology given to the text, after it was selected for reading:

[...] The selected texts must be properly discussed. Without organizing the contents of knowledge, we will have a bookish approach to the educational process. This approach, in turn, will be authoritarian and generate fear or individualism, driven by conveniences arising from the situation itself (SILVA, 1994, p. 7).

Here it can also be added that the text must not only be discussed, but also illustrated, recreated, parodied, paraphrased, staged, recited, synthesized, summarized, criticized, expanded. By doing so, he takes life, movement and makes the class more dynamic, challenging and interesting for the student.

However, if the teacher does not know how to treat the text in the classroom with due methodological care, he runs the risk of mystifying what is stated, as if it were an absolute truth, with no possibility of being questioned and criticized. In this way, the possibility of training student readers can become null or almost null. Discussion is essential so that the student never feels trapped and comes to understand that science evolves and that, what is close to a truth today, may not be or be very far from being so in a while. This attitude makes the student, as a citizen, start to question not only what is written, but the reality in which he is inserted and start to see, with that, possibilities of changes and advances not only in the external aspects, but even with itself, in its intrinsic, affective and cognitive aspects.

As the teacher's objective is to form an independent reader and writer student, it is necessary that he has the notion of how to apply these principles and methodologies that allow, in addition to the selection of the text, a dynamic and active discussion by the students. However, first of all, it is necessary for him to carry out the diagnostic assessment so that he

can have an approximate idea of the reading level at which the students are and, above all, the topics of interest. It is worth remembering that, due to Intellectual Disabilities, they sometimes manage to read books intended for younger students, because of the number of pages and pictures. However, it is necessary to remember that the topics covered in the text must correspond to their psychological maturity, that is, if they are mature as a teenager, it is necessary to offer the appropriate subjects, not infantilized.

An informal conversation between the teacher and the student and the availability of several books for reading, with summaries, prefaces, will help the student select the book he will read, as it will help him to anticipate what type of text he intends to read. For example, if the teacher says, this is a horror story book, this information will allow the student to get the idea that he will encounter characters and situations that will make him afraid. If the teacher says they are fairy tales, he will know that in the book they are arguing and planning to read about, the story is romantic and full of enchantment.

After all, what is anticipation?

It is when it becomes possible to predict what is to come, when the reader visualizes the support, reads abstracts, headlines, titles, prefaces. It is necessary to consider that the student is free to give up and choose another text to read, if that first one does not arouse his interest and the desire to continue reading, as he progresses in reading. This happens because as he reads, he makes inferences establishing interaction between his knowledge and the theme of the text and, if he discovers that that subject is not important or the book is too easy or too *complex*, he can choose another that he can read, which he believes to be within his reach and which promotes the challenge level, considered [*by himself*] to be ideal. In this regard, Izabel Solé (1998, p. 42) makes the following consideration: “For a person to be involved in a reading activity, it is necessary that they feel that they are able to read, to understand the text they have in their hands, both autonomously and with the help of more experienced others who act as support and resource.”

But what are inferences?

It can be said that they are the deductions raised by the reader, as he penetrates the text; but, which are not represented by the words written in the text. It is the implicit reading, for example: “He was a tall man, approximately 50 years old, with curly hair and yellow skin when he arrived at the hospital. The daughter, who was by her side, even if in a veiled way, was crying.” So that you have some kind of knowledge about the diseases that affect the Human Being, while reading you can infer that this man may have very serious liver problems. In the text, this information was not made explicit; but the clues given by him lead the reader to make

this kind of inference. It is worth remembering that the more prior knowledge one has on the subject, the more inferences the reader can make. This process is fundamental for him to build the meaning, sense and understanding of the subject that was read.

The teacher's role in this process is fundamental, as he can observe attitudes, analyze speeches and written or oral statements by the student or check, through simple and direct questions, if the student actually read the text and what types of inferences possible events happened while reading. Besides, of course, trying to understand what his reaction was after finishing the reading, whether of satisfaction or dissatisfaction. In the meantime, the teacher also needs to observe and try to understand why the student was unable to finish reading the text, if the text has a very difficult, complex language; if the text is too long or if, while reading, the student found that the text did not have as interesting a subject as he imagined.

Another reading strategy that the reader uses while performing the act of reading is verification.

But what is verification?

This is the moment that allows the reader to activate their feelings and sensitivity to judge whether the text, which they are reading, meets exactly the initial objective of seeking information, discovering something new or being distracted. As he reads, he checks whether or not what the author has written on the topic adds more information to what he already has and, above all, if they are useful for what he wants. Diving into the words, the structure of the text, its essence and its plot or line of thoughts allows the reader to refute, or not, the hypotheses that were raised from the title, abstract, headlines and other clues left by the author before the text itself.

And, finally, another and not the last reading strategy, text production.

Text production also takes place considering some aspects of textual coherence, the subject, objective, target audience, type of text that will be produced, whether literary or non-literary, the language that will be used, the structure, whether verses or paragraphs. Furthermore, the support, whether physical or online newspaper or book: blog sites, email, Twitter, Facebook, publishing platform, mural, billboard, serials, Comics, through which it will reach the reader. It is also necessary to consider whether it will be a short story, novel, novel, recipe, medicine leaflet, advertising leaflet, classified, note, law, instruction manual, news, editorial, abstracts, summary, preface, among others.

In this context, text production is the final result of the entire act of reading, since, within an interactionist approach, the text has its limits expanded due to the reader's previous knowledge and, with that, the reader himself will have his expanded knowledge through reading

and contact with the topic addressed in the text. It is new information that is added to the previous one; are more in-depth views on a particular topic. As a two-way street, the reader enriches his opinion by reading the text and the text takes on a hypertext character when the reader manages, through words and expressions, to add the sounds and images described, based on his experience of life of your linguistic baggage.

One way to verify this theory is to imagine, for example, that each reader will form a different image in front of the title *A Moreninha*. Only after reading the book can two different readers imagine a woman very close to the character created and described by the author, Joaquim Manoel Macedo (1820-1882). During the reading of the plot, the scenes described are formed according to the reader's knowledge of the time and place in which they take place. Those who do not know the Island of Paquetá or the city of Rio de Janeiro, do not have data to locate themselves in time/space, in relation to the facts themselves and the cardinal points.

As already stated, the reader, when proposing the practice of reading a text, has an objective, which can be to get informed, to acquire knowledge or to entertain himself, to feel pleasure with the beauty and aesthetics of the work. . That said, it is worth remembering that when these objectives are considered in the classroom, the teacher will be much more likely to witness his student reading. As the student reads with attention and dedication, he will broaden his knowledge of different types of subjects. In addition, it will enrich your vocabulary and improve the way you express yourself, both through speech and through writing. And it is at this moment that the teacher can explore these new discoveries, working and exploring both written textual productions and oral expression through workshops, reading techniques and text production.

And, the AEE teacher visualizing these possibilities for enriching reading strategies, will make his practice more encouraging and rich, with better conditions to train students with intellectual disabilities (ID) readers and writers, also including, of course, technology as a resource methodological.

READING AND PRODUCTION OF TEXTS WITH INTELLECTUALLY DISABLED STUDENTS (ID) IN AEE AS A MULTIDISCIPLINARY APPROACH

When having contact with the text to be read, especially the literary text, such as the fairy tale, we are faced with different situations inherent to the narrative text, such as character, fact, place, time, reason, consequences. In addition to the physical, psychological, attitudinal, behavioral description, beliefs, customs, entertainment of the character (Portuguese Language,

Philosophy, Sociology, Anthropology), account of the fact (fiction) that originated the narrative, the reader will find situations that will place him in a place (Geography) at a given time (History), foods that were served, animals that are part of the plot (Biological Sciences). There is always a background, through which it is possible to make various types of inferences, usually triggered by words, looks and attitudes described about the characters, their dwellings and customs.

If, for example, the tale *Cinderella and the Seven Dwarves*, in addition to the Portuguese Language, Geography, History, you can explore Genetics, the Chemistry of apple poison, Geology (dwarf ninas), types of metals explored in mines, metal smelting to make swords, types of metals, Physics (the temperature for smelting metals), Physical Education, sports such as horseback riding, fencing and all this approach may have a multidisciplinary character, since it is necessary to consider that where there is Human Being and Nature it is possible to approach, methodologically, all disciplines. These can be worked through searches on websites, *blogs*, books and *online encyclopedias*, and organized in the form of hypertexts.

When creating a short story, the author leaves his opinion on certain topics, recorded between the lines, that is, when he says, for example, “Once upon a time, there was a poor family, who lived in a very humble house, but that he never failed to attend church, where he thanked God for the little daily bread. Despite all the financial difficulties, the family lives together and happy. The father was a hardworking man, who faced crowded buses every day to go to the shoe factory. Until one day a drunk driver ran over his youngest son. It was a very hard blow for the family, as the driver fled the scene without providing assistance.”

Here you can see that the author may be a person who has values and who has faith, and who lives in a city, in which there is car traffic, alcoholic beverages, irresponsible people, but it may also be not, he may be an atheist. and, who may have read or heard a piece of news and decided to turn it into a story.

There are several possibilities for creating texts. The teacher will be able to start and explain to the student how to continue the story, using the knowledge he obtained through the other subjects. Sequences of engravings can be offered, techniques such as *Caixa Misteriosa*, texts to be enlarged such as the *Poema de Never Acabar*, to be recreated such as the poem *O Buraco do Tatu*, by the writer Sérgio Capparelli; transformation of newspaper news into short stories and vice versa; exhibition of films through which one can work on the production of reviews, summaries.

The most important thing in all of this is for the student to realize that there is a range of knowledge, which is worked on in the different disciplines and which he can use as resources

to create and re-create his texts. For example, the character might be a Biologist. As he knows what biology studies, he will be able to use this knowledge to enrich his texts. “Once upon a time there was a boy, whose name was João, who lived in a rich neighborhood in the big city and who was very curious. One afternoon when his mother was making dinner, he noticed that the water in the pot was bubbling and wanted to find out why it happened. The other day, when he arrived at school, he asked the teacher the reason for that phenomenon. The teacher took advantage of his question, took the class to the computer lab and conducted research there. Through research he discovered that...”. The text implies that the school had technological resources that allowed the teacher to carry out the research. And how much information can the student put in his text, if the teacher asks the right questions and creates a psycho-pedagogical environment suited to the creativity and inventiveness of the students?!

It is important to know that with the DI student, it is possible to work with all these possibilities, at their own pace, providing the materials they need, giving clear and objective guidelines, if possible contextualizing the plot with facts and situations of reality in the which it is inserted.

It is important that the teacher works with all types of text, since each one fulfills a social function, which is to take the author's idea to the receiver. However, a special space will be opened here for the literary text, since, through it, it is possible to work not only with information, but with sensitivity and feelings. In summary, the importance of literary reading for the formation of personality will be addressed, according to Morales (2000):

- a) **Source of Knowledge:** There is a utilitarian character of literature as a producer of artistic knowledge that is undoubtedly different from scientific knowledge. Through literary reading, the reader penetrates into worlds that, if not realities, are varied representations of it, thanks to the imagination of the authors, logically, it has its first support of reality. Literature offers truths about human nature and the society in which man develops. (...) it is much more than a representation of reality: it constitutes an enrichment of that reality.
- b) **Spiritual Strengthening:** Literature has a great perlocutionary force. It has a perlocutionary character, because when creating or reading it, it produces consequences or effects on the thoughts or actions in those who produce it and in those who read or listen to it. Tragedy produces emotions: compassion and fear; compassion for the protagonist and his sufferings and fear that the same may happen to the reader. The fact of savoring the text, finding a point of union between the message that emanates from the universe of the work and the universe of the reader is already gratifying: it ratifies the human condition.
- c) **Development of Intellect:** Reading is not a passive act, it requires the reader to put into operation a series of mental structures, which contributes to its development. It is a means for developing your power of analysis and

reasoning, it teaches you to think and understand reality in depth. Imagination, creativity, reflection are operations associated with reading and especially literature, hence it contributes to a greater structuring of thought.

d) Communicative Improvement: Every act of reading is an act of improving the use and handling of language, communication. And as our students read little literature, they speak and write worse and worse. Through reading, the reader has the possibility to prove the flexibility that are part of the language, inducing him to make an unusual, original use of it. It is an effective way to learn how to structure sentences of different types, increase vocabulary and punctuate correctly. Literary reading also improves knowledge due to the cooperative system that is established between the reader and the text in the reception process.

e) Provides delight: Literary reading provides knowledge, strengthens spiritually, develops the intellect and improves communication, delighting. Entering the pages of a work is an act that leads to pleasure, to the recreation of the spirit; it is a grateful stimulus that provokes emotions and allows entry into the worlds that are proposed by the texts and that the reader enriches with their experience and imagination (MORALES, 2000, pp. 11-16).

For these and other reasons that literary texts need to be worked in their entirety, since fragments and excerpts of literary texts do not provide the reader with the enchantment, the mystery, the magic, the suspense, the sensitivity that the text in its entirety carries with it. Whoever proposes to read, needs to be entangled by the text itself, and this encourages him to want to read it until the end, because the author creates strategies that hold attention and the will to want to continue. As you read, the question always comes up: *what will happen to such and such characters? Will they find their way home? Will they discover the treasure and become rich?* Here, a multidisciplinary approach to the act of reading is possible. For, in addition to inviting the reader to go around the world, the text invites him to dive into his own world and his own self.

It is still worth remembering that the reader is formed by reading and witnessing someone important in his social circle also reading; thus, it is important to offer texts that he is able to read, texts that arouse feelings such as love, anger, compassion, fear, surprises, mysteries; the best feelings in the reader's soul.

THE METHODOLOGICAL RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN READING AND WRITING AND THE STUDENT WITH MILD INTELLECTUAL DISABILITY

The text, to be a text, needs to be complete, with all its nuances and mysteries, with all its invitations and secrets, with all its execution possibilities, with all its linguistic possibilities and speech expressions. The text to be text needs to be cohesive and coherent with the communication situation for which it was written.

It is not uncommon, however, to find, in the midst of activities offered to students with mild intellectual disabilities, texts that are not actually texts. In general, they are a jumble of sentences, apparently organized in a narrative text, small, with easy-to-read language; but which, in essence, are devoid of enchantment and beauty.

Most of the time, they are childish texts, with titles that do not attract attention and do not arouse the desire to read. Little or no information can be gained from reading such pamphlets. The purpose of reading is to answer, at the end of the text, four or five questions for the teacher to find out if the student understood the text. In fact, there is not much to understand, the student only has to go to the text and copy the answer without having to think, because the questions are limited to the title of the text, author's name, the main character and the main fact, without any complications or climax.

It can be seen through the activities carried out, that teaching is based on the ascending and descending models of reading; in them, there is only the practice of linear reading, based on the mechanical decoding of words and the repetition of information from the text in the questions, without any significant or affective participation on the part of the student-reader. It is a bookish teaching, void of meaning and dynamism, which does not provide interaction between the reader and the text.

The methodological treatment given to reading, in the AEE, with students with Mild Intellectual Disabilities, needs to respect the same selection principles, considering the student's maturity and interest and, above all, make the objective clear, that is, if the texts are to be read in order to seek information, expand knowledge on the topic or for pleasure.

It cannot be forgotten that in addition to the reader's personal goals, it is also necessary to consider goals that need to be achieved throughout the teaching- learning process of reading so that this process becomes effective. According to Richard Bamberger (2000), Staiger (1973) highlights four points that need to be considered:

- a) Encouraging the full use of the individual's potential in their reading, in order to influence their well-being as much as possible and lead them to self-fulfillment.
- b) Efficient use of reading as a tool for learning and criticism, as well as relaxation and fun.
- c) Constant expansion of students' reading interests.
- d) Incentives to attitudes that lead to a permanent interest in reading many genres and for countless purposes. (STAIGER, 1973 apud BAMBERGER (2000, p. 24).

For this to happen, the texts need to be good and of unquestionable quality, in the sense of allowing the student to read and find the information they need, expand their knowledge in relation to the researched subject and have fun with characters and adventures lived by them. The texts, therefore, need to be in their entirety, so that the student can have contact with the literary work of art in all its magnitude and grandeur.

According to official recommendations listed in the National Curricular Parameters (BRASIL, 1997, 1998, 2007), for students with intellectual disabilities, adaptations in the curriculum must be analyzed and put into practice, which favor a satisfactory school performance and that take into account the expansion of their cognitive processes, aiming at the construction and mastery of written language.

In order for the AEE to comply with this determination, it is necessary to take the practice of reading based on the interactive model, considering that when the student reads, there is a two-way interaction between him and the text, at the same time that the text has its limits amplified due to the inferences made by the student as he reads. In this methodological sense, the text also expands the previous knowledge that the student brought with him, before reading the text. After all, as Richard Bamberger (2000, p. 12) says, “every human being can be helped by books to develop in their own way, they can increase their critical capacity and learn to choose between the mass of general production of the media. ”, including the target student of the Specialized Educational Service.

In the meantime, it is also necessary to rethink the methodological treatment given to the text, in the classroom routine. It has already been observed, in practice, that students with mild intellectual disabilities, in their time, can recreate, parody and paraphrase texts, can produce texts with the help of logical sequences of drawings; give continuity to proposed poems, illustrate, prepare film summaries, declaim poetry at soirees, organize videos with text presentations, sing song lyrics, invent original texts using techniques such as the magic box, staging, organize hypertexts through research and teacher guidelines, among others. Therefore, the teacher more than ever needs to rethink his practice in relation to the methodological treatment given to reading in the AEE and, above all, attention to the quality of the texts he offers his students to read.

THE *BLOG* AS ACTIVE METHODOLOGY TO IMPROVE TEXT READING AND PRODUCTION STRATEGIES WITH DI STUDENTS

The education system needs to insert technology into students' routine as a way to motivate them to attend schools. This is because, often, the student is already accustomed to the use of technology in their daily lives and cannot follow the lectures, in which only the teacher speaks. The use of texts and textbooks that fail to arouse the will to learn is also an aggravating factor in relation to the need to train students who are readers and writers. In this case, seeking technological resources as tools to encourage the active participation of students in classes can make a difference in the teaching-learning process, since technology promotes dynamism and updating in teaching plans.

The analysis of the different social networks available allowed us to understand that the use of the *Blog* appears to be the most ideal, since its structure organized into unlimited pages allows poetic texts, narratives, news, photos, videos, among others, to be published. , above all, that the results of the work carried out in the classroom are archived and at the same time made available to the public, as well as to the students themselves. This gives the *blog* the character of an electronic portfolio, which can be visited and commented on by Internet users.

In the view of Maria Teresa de Assunção Freitas (2007)

On the computer screen, the text manages to assume all its potential. It is the hypertext provided by cyberculture that allows a new way of reading/writing, establishing nodes, links with other texts and authors, creating varied and interpretive lines, merging the text with images and sounds, giving it a dynamism that is materialized in the possibility of taking different routes. On the computer screen, the reader selects the text that resides in a possible reserve of information, making an edit for himself, a singular montage. In this sense, the act of reading is an update of the meanings of a text, since the interpretation also includes an element of personal creation (FREITAS, 2002, pp. 162-163).

But what is the *blog* ?

According to Ariene Velasco,

A website that can be used both personally and professionally. The tool is responsible for allowing users to produce content and distribute ideas to other internet users. A blog has a very different structure from other sites, such as institutional or more traditional news portals. It can be made available on the web either through its own address (registered by the blog owner

himself) or through domains established by platforms such as Medium, which is widely used these days (2018, sp).

And, one of the uses is in the context of education as an active methodology, as it problematizes the contents to be researched, studied and produced by the students. Because, to keep the blog updated, it is necessary to have subjects and research results, literary productions to be published.

*Blogs emerged as an alternative to virtual spaces in the early days of the internet, such as forums and chat rooms, because people began to feel the need to have their own space to share their ideas. They started to become popular in the late 1990s, gaining even more popularity in the early 2000s when the first free *blog hosting platforms* began to emerge.*

The term comes from *weblog*, which means something like web log. This term was created in 1997 by John Barger and shortened to blog in 1999 by Peter Merholz, who, playing with the word weblog, split it into two parts to generate the phrase we blog. After that, little by little everyone adopted the abbreviation and the term blog was disseminated, and the most committed users began to be called bloggers, or, in the Brazilian version, bloggers. And it was in this context that the *Blogger* platform became one of the most important at that time, allowing anyone to create their own blog for free. By the way, PyraLabs, the company that created *Blogger*, was co-founded by Evan Williams, who is also a co-founder of *Twitter* and creator of *Medium*.

In the school context, students can produce their own texts and publish them on the *blog*, as well as explore different subjects in other *blogs*. To do this, they need to access the email address, access the Internet, enter the address and browse the *blog pages*, opening the titles according to their interest. This whole process can be called an active methodology, since it remains participatory and involved in the activity at all times. However, due to the fact that there are rules for publishing on a *blog*, it is necessary that the teacher has the access password, corrects texts and monitors publications, thus avoiding violating the principles of Ethics and Morals.

It is worth remembering that to prepare texts, students need to be constantly challenged in the practice of reading. That's because there's no way to write without having subjects. For this, the teacher needs to offer different types of texts linked in different supports, which can be websites, books, e-books, Comics, *blogs*, newspapers, magazines, among others. In addition, it is necessary to work with grammatical rules, when students will rewrite their texts for publication. As already mentioned, the internet allows the creation of hypertexts, in this sense, the student will feel more motivated with the possibility of also producing their own hypertexts,

enriching them with images, sounds, to give them greater dynamics and attract readers to the blog, maintained by him and the professor, in which his texts are being published.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

As an institution responsible for the formation of future generations, the school as a public and private institution cannot lose sight of the need to update itself, in the sense of inserting technological resources into its routine, to meet the interest of the demand, be it a student with a disability or a student without disabilities, which is updated in strides, with resources from outside the school.

It is necessary to consider that the role of the school is to train citizens who are able to continue learning even after completing their studies. For this, it is necessary to consider the methodological treatment that is given to reading and text production, by the teaching staff, especially the AEE teacher, towards the Mild Intellectual Disabled student.

In addition to outlining clear goals for teaching reading and writing, the teacher needs to use social networks, for example, the blog to encourage students to want to learn more, give visibility to their work and, above all, insert the technology of positively within the teaching-learning process.

Furthermore, one cannot lose sight of the importance of getting to know the student, his interest, his social context, his life project, believing, above all, in his talent, intelligence and creativity and, with that, working the true text and the production of text through techniques and workshops, in order to make it autonomous and capable of seeking continuous self-training and self-education.

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